

FRACTURE OF HYBRID COMPOSITE MATERIALS UNDER DYNAMIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

A method employing thin rings under dynamic internal pressure is described for testing composite materials at high strain rates. Unidirectional and angle-ply laminates of a carbon/S-glass/epoxy intraply hybrid material were tested at rates up to over 300 s⁻¹. Generally, moduli and strengths increase with strain rate. The increase is lowest in the longitudinal direction or for fiber dominated properties, and highest in the transverse direction, or for matrix-dominated properties. In all cases, including unidirectional longitudinal, transverse, and in-plane shear properties and uniaxial angle-ply properties, the ultimate strains did not vary significantly with strain rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Some applications of composite materials involve dynamically loaded components and structures. Dynamic loads range from low velocity impact to high velocity projectile impact and high energy shock loadings. The application of composites to such dynamically loaded structures requires knowledge of the loading pulse, induced wave propagation effects, and the response of the material to the high strain rates produced.

Most composite materials have been amply characterized under quasi-static conditions. Related work under dynamic conditions has been relatively limited. Testing of composites at high strain rates has been described by Rotem and Lifshitz [1,2], Sierakowski et al. [3], and Daniel and Liber [4-7]. In some of these tests, the specimen was a coupon loaded through grips by means of a falling weight or the piston of an electro-hydraulic system [1,2,4,5]. Hopkinson bar techniques are primarily suitable for compressive loading and utilize very small specimens [3].

In testing composite coupons at high strain rates, wave propagation effects become dominant and cause difficulties in the interpretation of results. A method was proposed and applied successfully that minimizes wave propagation effects [6,7]. This method utilizes a thin ring specimen loaded with a dynamic internal pressure pulse. The transit time of the stress wave across the thickness of the specimen is very short compared with the duration of the test.

The dynamic tensile behavior was studied of carbon/glass/epoxy hybrid composites in unidirectional and angle-ply configurations. Stress-strain curves to failure were obtained and longitudinal, transverse, in-plane shear, and uniaxial angle-ply properties were determined over a wide range of strain rates.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material characterized was carbon/S-glass/epoxy (80 AS/ 20 S/PR 288, 3M Company). This was an intraply hybrid composite with 80% AS carbon fiber and 20% S-glass fiber composite within the ply. The specimens were thin-wall cylinders (rings) 10.16 cm (4 in.) in outer diameter, 2.54 cm (1 in.) long and 6 to 8 plies thick. Unidirectional rings with fibers at 0°, 90° and 10° with the circumferential direction and angle-ply rings of $[\pm 15]_{2s}$, $[\pm 30]_{2s}$, $[\pm 45]_{2s}$, $[\pm 60]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 75]_{2s}$ layups were used. These specimens were cut from longer composite tubes which were fabricated with the desired fiber orientation and stacking sequence.

Dynamic testing was conducted by applying an internal pressure pulse explosively through a liquid in a specially designed fixture (Fig. 1). This fixture consists of two thick cylinders and two disks assembled together with the ring specimen between them to form one common reservoir. The pressure pulse in the fluid-filled chamber was produced by detonating an explosive charge in the liquid reservoir.

The dynamic internal pressure was originally measured with a piezoelectric transducer mounted on the side of the cylinder. Because of the large signal noise, this transducer was replaced with a steel calibration ring placed next to the composite ring specimen. This ring was made of Vascomax steel having a 2415 MPa (350 ksi) yield stress and a 193 GPa (28 x 10⁶ psi) modulus.

Strains on the composite and steel calibration rings were measured with strain gages mounted on the outer surfaces and recorded with a digital processing oscilloscope (Norland 2001A) at a rate of one point per microsecond.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis and interpretation of the dynamic data are based on the mechanics of a dynamically pressurized ring. The equation of motion of a ring sector of angle $d\theta$, simplified by assuming the ring thickness to be very small compared with the radius, is

$$\sigma_{\theta} h d\theta + \rho r h \ddot{u} d\theta - p a d\theta = 0 \quad (1)$$

or

$$p = \frac{h}{a} (\rho r \ddot{u} + \sigma_{\theta}) \quad (2)$$

where p = internal pressure

h = ring thickness

a = inner radius of ring

r = mean radius of ring

σ_{θ} = average circumferential stress in ring

The primary data recorded in the tests are

ϵ_{θ}^s = circumferential strain in steel calibration ring

ϵ_{θ}^c = circumferential strain in composite ring

ϵ_x^c = axial strain in composite ring

The circumferential stress in the steel ring is

$$\sigma_{\theta}^s = E^s \epsilon_{\theta}^s \quad (3)$$

and the dynamic pressure is obtained as

$$p = \frac{h_s}{a_s} (\rho_s r_s^2 \ddot{\epsilon}_\theta^s + \sigma_\theta^s) \quad (4)$$

where subscript or superscript *s* denote properties of steel.

The circumferential stress in the composite ring is obtained in terms of the pressure above and the second derivative of ϵ_θ^c as

$$\sigma_\theta^c = p \frac{a_c}{h_c} - \rho_c r_c^2 \ddot{\epsilon}_\theta^c \quad (5)$$

where subscript and superscript *c* denote composite properties. The dynamic stress-strain curve for the composite material was obtained by plotting σ_θ^c versus ϵ_θ^c . Moduli, Poisson's ratios, strength, and ultimate strains for the composite material were thus obtained from the recorded and computed data. In the computations above, it is necessary to obtain second derivatives of experimental data, a task which is very difficult to do with precision. A procedure involving smoothing operations and approximations was developed and incorporated into a simple data processing program [6].

4. RESULTS

4.1 Longitudinal Tensile Properties

Typical stress-strain curves to failure under quasi-static, and high rates of loading are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 for the 80 AS/20 S/PR 288 material in the fiber direction. Two to three specimens were tested in every case. Numerical results are tabulated in Table 1. The variation of modulus, both initial and secant, is plotted versus strain rate in Fig. 4. Results for two other carbon/epoxy composites are also shown in this figure for comparison. Results show that the modulus, being a fiber dominated property, increases only moderately (approximately 10%) with strain rate, with only one exception in the case of initial modulus at the highest strain rate. The strength and ultimate strain show some slight reduction with increasing strain rate, although the trend may not be significant in view of the scatter in experimental results.

TABLE 1. Longitudinal tensile properties of unidirectional carbon/S-glass/epoxy at various strain rates

Property	Average Strain Rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_1$ (s^{-1})		
	1×10^{-4}	49	268
Initial Modulus, E_1 , GPa (Msi)	107 (15.6)	117 (16.9)	170 (24.7)
Secant Modulus, E_1 , GPa (Msi)	109 (15.8)	118 (17.1)	112 (16.2)
Time to Failure, t_f , (μs)	1×10^8	203	40
Strength, F_{1t} MPa (ksi)	1240 (180)	1162 (168)	1129 (164)
Ultimate Strain, ϵ_{1t}^u	0.0115	0.0099	0.0103

Fig. 1 Fixture for dynamic loading of composite ring specimens

Fig. 2 Stress-strain curves for unidirectional carbon/S-glass/epoxy under quasi-static longitudinal tensile loading

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curve for unidirectional carbon/S-glass/epoxy under high rate longitudinal tensile loading

Fig. 4 Ratio of dynamic to static longitudinal modulus for three materials as a function of strain rate

4.2 Transverse Tensile Properties

Stress-strain curves to failure under quasi-static and high rates of loading are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. Results are tabulated in Table 2. The variation of secant modulus with strain rate is plotted in Fig. 7, where it is compared with results for two other carbon/epoxy composites. It is seen that both transverse modulus and transverse strength which are matrix dominated properties increase sharply with strain rate. The ultimate strain fluctuates without any definite trend, but most likely does not vary with strain rate in any significant way.

TABLE 2. Transverse tensile properties of unidirectional carbon/S-glass/epoxy at various strain rates

Property	Average Strain Rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_2$ (s ⁻¹)		
	1×10^{-4}	36	98
Initial Modulus, E_2 , GPa (Msi)	11.8 (1.71)	26.1 (3.78)	42.8 (6.21)
Secant Modulus, E_2 , GPa (Msi)	11.1 (1.61)	20.7 (3.00)	27.9 (4.05)
Time to Failure, t_f , (μ s)	1×10^8	56	64
Strength, F_{2t} MPa (ksi)	49 (7.1)	39 (5.6)	174 (25.2)
Ultimate Strain, ϵ_{2t}^u	0.0045	0.0019	0.0062

Fig. 5 Stress-strain curves for unidirectional carbon/S-glass/epoxy under quasi-static transverse tensile loading

Fig. 6 Stress-strain curves for unidirectional carbon/S-glass/epoxy under high rate transverse tensile loading

4.3 In-Plane Shear Properties

In-plane shear properties were obtained by testing rings of the unidirectional material with the fibers oriented at 10° with the circumferential direction [6,7]. Shear stress versus shear strain curves under quasi-static, and high rates of loading are shown in Figs. 8 and 9. Results are tabulated in Table 3. The variation of both initial and secant moduli with strain rate is plotted in Fig. 10, where it is compared with results for two other carbon/epoxy composites. It is seen that the initial modulus increases by up to 32% and the shear strength by up to 50%. However, the ultimate in-plane shear strain does not vary significantly with strain rate.

TABLE 3. In-plane shear properties of unidirectional, carbon/S-glass/epoxy at various strain rates

Property	Average Strain Rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_{12}$ (s^{-1})		
	1×10^{-4}	51	186
Initial Modulus, G_{12} , GPa (Msi)	6.9 (1.00)	8.7 (1.27)	9.1 (1.32)
Secant Modulus, G_{12} , GPa (Msi)	4.3 (0.62)	6.1 (0.89)	5.3 (0.77)
Time to Failure, t_f , (μs)	1×10^8	171	46
Strength, F_{12} MPa (ksi)	66 (9.6)	102 (14.7)	78 (11.2)
Ultimate Strain, $\gamma_{12}^u = 2\epsilon_{12}^u$	0.0156	0.0168	0.0144

Fig. 7 Ratio of dynamic to static transverse secant modulus for three materials as a function of strain rate

Fig. 8 Shear stress versus shear strain for unidirectional carbon/S-glass/epoxy under quasi-static in-plane shear loading

Fig. 9 Shear stress versus shear strain for unidirectional carbon/S-Glass/epoxy under high-rate in-plane shear loading

Fig. 10 Ratio of dynamic to static in-plane shear modulus for three materials as a function of strain rate

4.4 Angle-Ply Tensile Properties

Similar results were obtained for angle-ply laminates of $[\pm\theta]_{2s}$ layup with $\theta = 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ$ and 75° . Results for the $[\pm 30]_{2s}$ layup are tabulated in Table 4. It is seen that both modulus and strength, with one exception, increase moderately with strain rate. The ultimate strain, as for all cases before, did not vary significantly with strain rate. Results for the other angle-ply layups showed that modulus and strength for fiber dominated layups, e.g., $[\pm 15]_{2s}$, increase moderately with strain rate. A much sharper increase in modulus and strength was noted for matrix-dominated layups such as the $[\pm 60]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 75]_{2s}$ laminates.

TABLE 4. Axial tensile properties of $[\pm 30]_{2s}$ angle-ply carbon/S-glass epoxy laminate at various strain rates

Property	Average Strain Rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_x$ (s^{-1})		
	1×10^{-4}	72	324
Initial Modulus, \bar{E}_x , GPa (Msi)	44.9 (6.51)	43.5 (6.31)	93.5 (13.6)
Secant Modulus, \bar{E}_x , GPa (Msi)	36.2 (5.25)	41.9 (6.07)	51.5 (7.50)
Time to Failure, t_f , (μs)	2×10^8	201	42
Strength, \bar{F}_{xt} , MPa (ksi)	503 (73)	611 (89)	690 (100)
Ultimate Strain, $\bar{\epsilon}_{xt}^u$	0.0141	0.0144	0.0135

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A method employing thin rings under internal pressure was described for testing composite materials under high tensile strain rates. The stress-strain behavior and strength were determined of a carbon/S-glass/epoxy intraply hybrid material at strain rates ranging from quasi-static to over 300 s^{-1} . Longitudinal, transverse and in-plane shear properties were determined of the unidirectional material and uniaxial tensile properties were measured of angle-ply laminates of the same material.

The longitudinal modulus, being a fiber dominated property, increases moderately with strain rate. The longitudinal strength and ultimate strain show some slight reduction, although no significant trend with strain rate can be proven.

Transverse modulus and transverse tensile strength, being matrix dominated properties, increase appreciably with strain rate. However, the ultimate transverse tensile strain does not vary significantly.

Under in-plane shear loading it was found that both initial shear modulus and strength increase with strain rate. However, the ultimate in-plane shear strain does not vary significantly with strain rate.

The axial modulus and tensile strength of $[\pm\theta]_{2s}$ angle-ply laminates, increase moderately for fiber-dominated layups ($\theta \leq 30^\circ$) and appreciably for matrix dominated layups ($\theta > 45^\circ$). As in the previous cases, the ultimate strains do not vary significantly with strain rate.

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